

**TEACHING IN HIGHER EDUCATION IN CAMEROON: CHALLENGES AND PROSPECTS
FOR ACADEMICS WITH VISUAL IMPAIRMENT**

Nyugap, Charly Ringyu

Faculty of Education, University of Buea, Cameroon

nyugapcharly@gmail.com

and

Ngwa, Emmanuel Shu

²Faculty of Education, University of Bamenda, Cameroon

Abstract

This paper focused on “Teaching in Higher Education in Cameroon: Challenges and Prospects for Academics with Visual Impairment”. The paper, using interview-generated data, thematically explored the views of academics with visual impairment pertaining to the challenges they face in the course of teaching in Higher Education in Cameroon, with focus on their tri-function responsibilities - Teaching, Research and Community Outreach. The discussion was theoretically underpinned by the Social Model of Disability by Michael Oliver and the Change Model of Kurt Lewin. As a qualitative study, the paper employed the exploratory research design, making a purposive use of three lecturers with visual impairment (VI) in Higher Education (HE) institutions. The findings revealed that lecturers with visual impairment face challenges such as; negative attitude towards them by stakeholders, inadequate Assistive Technological devices, inadequate access to information for teaching/research and financial constraints due to extra cost of coping as academics with VI. From the basis of the findings, recommendations were made that might go a long way to increase the prospects of lecturers with VI in Cameroon universities and enhance quality inclusive HE education, thereby accelerating the realization of the global Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) as well as Cameroon’s national development agenda. These include the formulation and effective implementation of inclusive policies, sensitization to advocate positive change of attitude towards persons with VI, provision of subventions for them, construction of infrastructure that facilitate mobility, the establishment of resource centers on university campuses equipped with Assistive Technological devices and the employment of scribes to assist the lecturers with VI.

Keywords: Higher education; Higher Education in Cameroon; Academics; Visual impairment

Introduction

Our mainstream educational institutions nowadays are increasingly made up of persons with diverse characteristics, including those with disabilities. This has caused the idea of inclusion to become more inevitable hence a current trend in the educational system. Given that higher education plays a critical role in promoting societal values and development policies, it has equally seen the need to adopt strategies to enhance inclusion. An inclusive education system enables learners with special needs to equally and equitably benefit in mainstream classrooms as “normal” learners (Kirschner, 2015 & Nyugap and Ngwa, 2015). This implies that learners with visual impairment, who are part of those with special needs upon graduation, should be provided an inclusive society for them to fit in as citizens who also possess the right to contribute to national development through their involvement in different career paths, including teaching in higher education institutions.

In recent years, teaching within the Cameroon university system has embraced a key innovation by gradually hiring the services of academic staff or lecturers with visual impairment. The implication here is that the idea of inclusion should be extended to the staff and other non-student stakeholders. Inclusive education therefore is to enable persons with special needs including those with visual impairment to be able to pick up roles to enhance progress in the

society. Among these persons are those who end up as teachers in Higher Education, hence they also need to be accommodated within the school system. Life is all about diversity. This implies that every field should consider persons from different backgrounds and with varying characteristics. Academics with visual impairment range from those with cases of partial sight to complete blindness (Mushome & Manobe, 2013). They face similar challenges as those faced by learners with visual impairment but their case is more severe because they have to teach or train diverse learners. These challenges include the negative perception of students and some staff members towards lecturers with visual impairment, infrastructural challenges, inadequacy of assistive technological devices and special aids, and challenges in assessment (Koutsoklenis, 2011; Nyugap and Ngwa, 2015).

However, the efforts so far made by stakeholders to enhance inclusion in the educational system are insufficient and limited to students, with little consideration for lecturers with visual impairment who equally possess the potential to enhance quality education in Cameroon universities. This paper therefore explores the opinions of some of these lecturers with visual impairment with focus on the challenges they encounter in performing their tri-function responsibilities of teaching, research and community outreach, and a possible way forward.

Statement of the Problem

Inclusive Education has been a frontline affair for decades since 1994 when it was ratified at the Salamanca Conference but limited efforts have been made to promote it. Cameroon actually started giving some considerable attention to issues of inclusive education in 2013, and so it is expected that she should have made some progress by now, especially in Higher Education where greater professional specialization takes place. This, however appears not to be the case as repeatedly observed. Instead of the Higher Education system to change towards accommodating the needs of lecturers with visual impairment, inclusion at this level is still so limited that the staff with visual impairment are seen to be the ones struggling to accommodate the system. Policies and decisions are still made without considering them and they still experience discrimination and stigmatization among other vices. The academic staff with visual impairment only manage to cope with negative attitudes towards them in the system. Since attitude appears not to have changed, the physical environment has not changed much either. Even in newly created universities, little is being done to construct a disability friendly environment. For instance, the University of Bamenda campus is having newly constructed buildings with no facilities to enhance the mobility of persons with disabilities. The Cameroon Baptist Convention (CBC) has intervened to construct ramps to the laboratory, canteen, some lecture rooms, and has offered some assistive technological devices, which are still insufficient as compared to the required level of accommodation. Besides, the CBC cannot provide all the required facilities to enhance effective accommodation of staff and students with visual impairment who need to carry out teaching-learning activities, research and also community outreach. It is obvious that under such circumstances, Higher Education in the country remains in its objective to promote a society that inclusively meets the 21st century expectations. This situation is a major hindrance to the realization of Higher Education goals, and the Cameroon Government's national development strategy by which the country is expected to be an Emerging Nation by the year 2035, as well as the attainment of the global SDGs. In the phase of these observations, this paper thus seeks to explore the opinions of academic staff with visual impairment in Cameroon's public and private higher institutions with regards to the challenges in the execution of their tri-function responsibilities and a possible way forward.

Review of Related Literature

Higher Education in Cameroon

Higher Education is at the top of the Education System and plays a leading role in sustainable development, and so it has become more of a necessity than a luxury. Beginning with the University of Yaounde I established after independence in 1961, there are currently 10 state universities in Cameroon and over 250 professional institutions under the Ministry of Higher Education (MINESUP). Higher Education refers to organized tertiary teaching/learning institutions after secondary school (Alemu, 2018). Higher Education in Cameroon is provided by the state, missions

and lay private individuals, employing staff with diverse characteristics but all focused on the general aim as stipulated in Law No. 98/004 of 1 April 1998 which is to enhance smooth integration of children into society bearing in mind the prevailing economic, socio-cultural, political and moral factors (Monono et al, 2018). The general mission of Higher Education in Cameroon as stated by Oben (2021), is “to produce, organize and disseminate scientific, cultural, professional and ethical knowledge for the purpose of development”. Higher Educational institutions provide both undergraduate and postgraduate studies and awards professional Diplomas, Bachelor degrees, Master degrees and the PhD for meritorious students/graduates.

Teaching in Higher Education

Teaching in Higher Education as in all other levels of formal teaching/learning refers to all the activities and processes that enhance the development of knowledge, skills and aptitudes by students to enable them assume various roles in society and engage in sustainable development. With the widening student diversity and increasing use of technology at this level, teaching has generally become more challenging, especially to lecturers with visual impairment. Teaching in higher education involves actual teaching, research and community outreach. The teaching task requires the lecturer to thoroughly understand the students with diversities and how they learn, plan teaching/learning based on a carefully designed curriculum, lecture groups of varying sizes and from different backgrounds, enhance E-learning, attain to students’ challenges, continuously assess students’ learning, assign and supervise students’ research while managing disruptive behaviour (Fry, Ketteridge & Marshall, 2009). It involves a careful selection of suitable methods such as the Dalton plan, project method, heuristic method, seminar method, demonstration method amongst others (Walters & Rangaswamy, 2021).

Research in Higher Education plays a great role in influencing the quality of teaching and students’ learning (Cabral & Huet, 2011). Research enables both the lecturers and the students to find solutions to problems in the various fields hence develop new knowledge, skills and aptitudes needed to enhance progress in the society. The lecturer carries out research to improve on the quality of teaching in line with the changing world. In addition to this, proper supervision of students’ research both at the undergraduate and postgraduate levels is a great task for the lecturer. In this regard, research has to be incorporated into the teaching process. It is more challenging for lecturers with visual impairment as they need more assistive devices to meet up and even suffer from negative attitudes from colleagues and supervisees.

Community outreach is another very important task for lecturers in Higher education. It involves engaging the community in the teaching/learning system to make education more concrete with contemporary development issues. It orientates students with realities outside the university walls and helps them better fit into the wider society and become more useful. Higher education institutions therefore organize regular engagements with partners and other organizations to make the system more worthy (Johnson, Danvers, Smith & Atkinson, 2019). Successful community outreach for lecturers with visual impairment requires positive attitudes, disability friendly policies and assistive measures.

Teaching with Visual Impairment

As earlier mentioned, the requirements for learners with visual impairment to cope are similar to those for lecturers with visual impairment to meet up with their duty in Higher Education. According to Sefotho and Ferreira (2020), learners and teachers with visual impairment need to have the same opportunities as those without special needs. This requires that stakeholders in Higher Education should provide adequate care, and enhance the development of high self-esteem and self-efficacy for them. In the absence of these, it will be difficult for them to execute their duties. It is necessary to facilitate constant capacity building by providing improved resources and infrastructure as well as formulating policies or making decisions that consider the situation of lecturers with visual impairment. In this light,

as Ferreira puts it, the establishment of a support team assigned with the duty to ensure inclusion in the system is inevitable.

Academics with visual impairment need a lot of Assistive Technology (AT) to conduct assessment which is a key aspect in teaching. This includes AT for reading, writing and access to computers (software and hardware). The AT for reading includes: braille text, braille labeler, audio books and digital text. For writing, they require enough adaptive papers, slates and styluses, word processors, manuals and electronic braille writers and braille embossers. To facilitate orientation and mobility for lecturers with visual impairment, the campus needs low tech adaptations, canes, enlarged braille or talking campus, electronic travel aids and GPS devices (Tebo, 2022). The absence of these facilities might hinder the smooth execution of their duties of teaching and assessing students in Higher Education.

Challenges Faced by Academics with Visual Impairment in Higher Education

Lecturers with visual impairment encounter challenges in different dimensions in the course of executing their duty in Higher Education. These challenges make it difficult for the potentials in them to be adequately utilized. These challenges are similarly those faced by students with visual impairment in mainstream schools. As the students graduate and pursue postgraduate studies, some of them end up in the teaching field as lecturers in Higher Education. Most studies in this light have been focused on students but they reveal relevant literature on challenges which lecturers with visual impairment are likely to face. Such challenges include financial constraints, stigmatization, mobility challenges and inaccessibility to teaching/learning resources.

Financial constraints are said to hinder efficiency of teachers with visual impairment. According to Nyugap and Ngwa (2015), most higher institutions in Central Africa and Cameroon in particular have failed to make their campuses and services adaptable to the needs of learners and staff with visual impairments. Consequently, these staff and students need extra financial resources to successfully engage in the teaching-learning process which is often done at their own expense. The staff particularly need to hire the services of sighted readers to serve as personal assistants, and sighted braille experts who can serve as transcribers. Therefore, if research allowances are limited or not timely provided, their work becomes more challenging (Amin et al., 2021).

Stigmatization is another impediment to efficiency for teachers with visual impairment. This involves labeling and negative attitude. Just like students with visual impairment encounter challenges in smooth relationship and effective communication with their peers, lecturers with visual impairment are not spared of similar problems with other members of the system. If other staff do not cultivate and accommodating attitude towards them, it might be difficult for lecturers with visual impairment to effectively meet up with their duty requirement.

Closely linked to negative attitudes is the laxity of stakeholders to establish and enforce clear policies of Inclusive Education to facilitate the work of lecturers with visual impairment. The idea of Inclusion has been a major concern in our educational system for decades but so far, it is more of theory than practice. Little effort is made by the stakeholders to enforce the practice, scrutiny and evaluation of inclusive Education policies. This might have an adverse effect on efficiency of lecturers with visual impairment (Mbibeh, 2013).

Mobility challenges/inaccessibility within the environment can equally impede the smooth execution of duties by lecturers with visual impairment as it does to students in this situation. The physical environment needs to be constructed in a way to facilitate mobility of lecturers with visual impairment. This includes the construction of rounds, establishment of technological devices that support movement, a talking campus and GPS amongst other measures (Yalo, Indoshi, Agak, & Were, 2010). The construction of the school environment without considering the situation of students and lecturers with visual impairment and other cases of impairment is simply imposing a disability on them.

Inadequate provision of audio, optical and non-optical devices can equally render lecturers with visual impairment less efficient in performing their duties. The use of audio devices, digital texts, word processors, specialized computers amongst other Assistive Devices greatly enhance research for lecturers with visual impairment (Agesa, 2014).

Theoretical Framework

This study is underpinned by the Social Model of Disability propounded by Michael Oliver and the Change Model of Kurt Lewin.

The Social Model of Michael Oliver (1973)

This theory is focused on the way society views and treats persons with impairments. Its proponent believes that the impediments encountered by persons with disabilities are imposed by the society hence disability is viewed as socially constructed. In this light, the social model defines disability as the social barriers imposed on persons with physical, sensory or cognitive impairments which limit them from fully participating in the society (Oliver 2013). Such barriers range from derogatory attitude, stigmatization and social exclusion. It holds that persons with impairments will carry out their day-to-day activities easily if the society provides enabling structures for them. Mike believes that the wellbeing of persons with impairments is determined by the way society is organized hence he attributes disability to attitudinal, physical and Information/Communication barriers.

In line with this model, lecturers in Higher Education would perform their duties effectively and efficiently if the attitude of stakeholders, the physical environment in terms of infrastructure, and information/communication tools are disability friendly. This implies that if authorities make decisions without considering the situation of these lecturers, if the school infrastructure is not adapted to their needs, and if assistive technology to enhance communication is not adequately provided, lecturers with visual impairment might become “disabled”. This is why the Social Model of Disability recommends an adequate income, social care and healthcare provisions, accessible environment, adequate provision of technological equipment, availability of advocacy, and the provision of equal opportunities to enable persons with impairments gain accommodation in the various systems (Temesgen, 2018).

Kurt Lewin’s Change Model (1947)

In his Change Model, Kurt Lewin believes that organizations need to be flexible in order to meet up with a highly competing and complex world. This change has to come in a carefully planned and organized manner to be successful. He proposes three successive stages of organizational change: unfreezing, movement and freezing. Unfreezing is the first phase in planned organizational change, and involves fact finding and establishment of the need for change. By unfreezing, members of the organization are made to understand the problem with the current state of affairs and the reason to discontinue in that state. This is followed by the second phase-movement where there is a displacement of the status quo of organizational norms and values. The change is made at this level. This requires the use of experts as the change might meet resistance from some members. Unfreezing is the last stage, involving acceptance to the change by members affected as they now see the change worthwhile. At this point, the new phenomena are firmly established (Alvesson & Sveningsson, 2008).

In view of Lewin’s model, the idea of effecting possible changes in Higher Education systems to more effectively accommodate lecturers with visual impairment is necessary for them to be successful. This will involve a gradual change of attitude, decision making, physical infrastructure and technological systems as the need may be.

Methodology

This exercise was a Qualitative study which employed the Exploratory Research Design with a target population of 5 academics with visual impairment in Higher Education institutions across Cameroon – notably the University of Buea, University of Yaounde 1, University of Yaounde II, Higher Teacher Training College (ENS) Yaounde and the

Chattered Higher Institute of Technology and Management (CHITECHMA) Buea who were purposively selected. A structured interview guide was used to collect data from these lecturers with a participation rate of 85 percent. The respondents were coded as R1, R2, R3 and R 4. The items on the interview guide were based on their experiences and opinions as far as the tri-functional duties were concerned. The Thematic approach was employed to analyze the data, whereby the lecturers' opinions pertaining to the issues regarding the execution of their tri-functional responsibilities in their respective institutions were developed into major themes and discussed using the integrated approach.

Findings and Discussions

After listening to what they experience in teaching, research and community outreach, their views were summarized into five key themes: negative attitudes, inadequate Assistive Technology (AT), financial constraints, mobility challenges and inadequate access to information.

Negative Attitudes

The respondents repeatedly cried that negative attitudes from some members of their institution is a major impediment to efficient and effective execution of their duties. This is often experienced right at the level of recruitment. R2 clearly stated that

“I was recruited in 2011 when the president launched the employment scheme of 25,000 and posted to the University of Yaounde 1 but the authorities dropped me when they realized that I am visually impaired”. I had to write to the minister before I was finally recruited. Even in the course of working, they still experience some sort of stigmatization as R1 stated that “some colleagues hesitate to work with me because I am visually impaired”.

When it comes to research, some are assigned a smaller number of supervisees on grounds that they have a disability. Students also take advantage and throw negative comments at these lecturers because they cannot be seen. In conformity with the view of Mbibeh (2013), such an attitude has an adverse effect on the work of lecturers with visual impairment.

Inadequate AT

All the interviewed lecturers with visual impairment indicated that their work is often impeded by inadequate AT. All of them possess a personal laptop but it is insufficient because any breakdown will frustrate progress. They equally indicated that the libraries are not adapted to their condition hence they often employ an assistant. These devices are not easily found in the markets in Cameroon as R3 put it,

“it is difficult to acquire electronic and assistive devices and the original software in this country”.

All of them indicated that the system has not provided the necessary equipment hence they go through the stress of acquiring them personally, which slows down their work. This is in line with Agesa (2014), who opined that the absence of necessary technological equipment hinders effective teaching/learning for persons with visual impairment.

Mobility Challenges

The interviewed lecturers with visual impairment indicated that movement on campus is difficult because it is not constructed to meet the needs of persons with impairments. They require a guide to go to the lecture rooms since there is no talking campus. According to them, mobility is more challenging in the classroom as it is inevitable in classroom management. R2 stated that even though the campus of ENS Yaounde is disability friendly outside the classroom, “sometimes I don't move to avoid the risk of falling since the amphitheatres have staircases”. They also encounter mobility challenges when going to the field for data collection in line with the research aspect of teaching given that they cannot explore the physical environment as other lecturers without impairment. This implies that the environment is relatively inaccessible for them. It therefore agrees with Yalo, Indoshi, Agak, and Were (2010) who

indicated that the absence of a talking campus, assistive technology that supports movement and GPS does not favour persons with visual impairment.

Inadequate Access to Information

The respondents repeatedly indicated that they encounter difficulties in accessing information to prepare lessons. Such information is expected to be available in libraries but unfortunately, the libraries are not adapted to users with visual impairment. As R2 put it, “I cannot use the library without assistance from someone who guides me since it is not adapted to the condition of persons with visual impairment”. Though few electronic books are available in some libraries, they hardly meet the current requirements. For instance, R3 stated that “electronic books are available in the library but do not fit accurately with the material needed to prepare lessons, and the procedure of obtaining the university password is stressful”. Accessing information on the internet is equally challenging because someone must assist as R3 says “I possess skills in sourcing online but an assistant is needed and the use of audio is a complex procedure”. Therefore, it is very challenging to access information for lesson preparation and for research.

Financial Constraints

All the respondents indicated that their financial resources are limited given that they make extra expenditures in the course of performing their duties. All lecturers face financial constraints because of the current economic situation but the case of those with visual impairment is more severe because they require extra expenditure to hire the services of assistants and/or guides. For instance, R2 said “I make double expenditure as compared to other lecturers because I must hire someone, pay for his transportation and lodging to assist me in collecting data in the course of research”. Extra expenditures are also made in affording AT devices given that they are not readily available and are imported at higher prices. Sometimes they make additional expenditure to transcribe hard copy texts to be able to read. R2 states that “I bought a book for 15,000FCFA and spent 80,000FCFA in a Handicap Centre to have it transcribed”. This implies that he spent 95,000FCFA for a book that costs 15,000FCFA. The extra expenses increase their financial burden hence makes their work more challenging. This matches with the opinion of Amin et al (2021) who believe that inadequate financial resources impede the efforts of persons with visual impairment.

From the above findings and discussions, more efforts have to be made in order to facilitate teaching in Higher Education for lecturers with visual impairment.

Prospects for Academics with Visual Impairment

The respondents proposed some solutions that can reduce the above challenges and improve on their duty of teaching in higher education. From their response, the lecturers with visual impairment will be more accommodated they will be more accommodated if the following measures are adopted and/or implemented:

- Thorough sensitization through seminars and the media to change the attitude of the stakeholders of Higher Education and the general society towards persons with visual impairment.
- Adequate provision of AT devices and available secretaries employed by the institution to assist lecturers with visual impairment periodically.
- Better subventions or research allowances for lecturers with visual impairment to more easily meet up with extra expenditure in the course of research and in sourcing necessary information.
- Effective implementation of the 2010 law on inclusion and effective follow up by the supra system to ensure implementation of inclusive policies.
- Establishment of a special centre for ready supply of AT materials in the country.

Conclusion

This study was aimed at exploring the views of lecturers with visual impairments in Higher Education in Cameroon pertaining to the challenges encountered in the course of executing their tri-function services of teaching, research

and community outreach, as well as the prospects. The exploratory research design was employed and interviews conducted on 4 lecturers across the country. The data was thematically analysed and from the findings it was concluded that negative attitudes of stakeholders, inadequate assistive technology, mobility challenges, inadequate access to information and financial constraints are major challenges to lecturers with visual impairment in higher education institutions in Cameroon. These findings concur with the social model of Michael Oliver that society imposes disabilities on these lecturers who equally have potentials needed to enhance national development. It was equally agreed that in line with the change model of Kurt Lewin that the society and its stakeholders need to reconsider persons with visual impairment and remove the disabilities imposed on them. Lecturers with visual impairment possess potentials needed to attain the vision of Higher Education. These potentials can only be fully utilized if policies are formulated and facilities provided to effectively accommodate them in the system.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, some measures are required to facilitate the work of lecturers with visual impairment thus making Higher education in Cameroon more accommodating. These measures however should be adapted to the country's economic situation and level of technological advancement. In addition to the prospects proposed by the interviewees, the following recommendations will go a long way to remove the disabilities imposed on lecturers with VI hence empower them to be more efficient, effective and relatively independent in the execution of their tri-functional duty of teaching in Higher education.

Higher education authorities and the supra system should train and recruit readily available experts to transcribe material into braille. This will enable lecturers with VI to study concepts and contents in greater detail, enjoy privacy in sourcing material and in preparing lessons.

Workshops/seminars should be organized in Higher education institutions to raise awareness on the need for members to adopt a positive attitude towards lecturers with VI. This should be focused on eliminating all forms of discrimination, disregard and stigmatization against them. Sensitization should also be intensified through the media for the public to understand, recognize and accept persons with impairments in general, and lecturers with VI in particular.

Team teaching or co-teaching should be promoted in Higher education. This means that at least two lecturers should be assigned to each course so as to avoid frustration in case a lecturer is absent. For co-teaching to be more meaningful, lecturers with VI should be paired with those without impairment. In this case, classroom management and assessment of learners will be more successful.

Policies should also be formulated to ensure effective accommodation of lecturers with VI in Higher Education in Cameroon. This should include the recruitment policies and provision of subventions to facilitate their work. The policies should also regulate the construction of physical infrastructure that allows mobility of lecturers with VI.

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